

الهيئة الليبية للبحث العلمي

المركز الليبي لبحوث التقنيات الحيوية

المركز الليبي لبحوث التقنيات الحيوية

المؤتمر السابع
للتقنيات الحيوية

تحت شعار
دور التقنيات الحيوية في خدمة المجتمع

كتيب
المستخلصات

2024 | 25-24
فبراير

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المقدمة

إنه لمن دواعي الفرح والفخر والاعتزاز أن يُقيم المركز الليبي لبحوث التقنيات الحيوية هذا المؤتمر تحت شعار: (دور التقنيات الحيوية في خدمة المجتمع).

فالمركز الليبي لبحوث التقنيات الحيوية أصبح اليوم واحداً من مؤسسات التعليم العالي الرائدة في مجال الأبحاث العلمية فهو يضم نخبة متميزة من أعضاء هيئة التدريس والباحثين القادرين على إنتاج الأبحاث المتميزة وتطوير وربط الأبحاث العلمية التطبيقية بكافة مجالات التقنيات الحيوية التي تُلبي إحتياجات المجتمع الليبي ذات الأولوية الوطنية كما يقوم المركز بتقديم الاستشارات الفنية والدراسات الميدانية مع توفير وتيسير السبل اللازمة للانفتاح العلمى وتبادل الخبرات مع كافة المؤسسات العلمية.

وتكمن أهمية هذا المؤتمر العلمى الدولى فى إتاحة الفرصة للباحثين والمهتمين بمجالات التقنية الحيوية للقاء والتحاور وتبادل المعارف والخبرات فى المجالات العلمية والقضايا البحثية المشتركة وتعزيز دور التقنيات الحيوية فى خدمة المجتمع وتلبية إحتياجاته وتعزيز العلاقة مع مؤسسات الدولة والهيئات والمراكز العلمية وتقييم أهم المشكلات البيئية والصحية والزراعية واقتراح الحلول العلمية المناسبة لها.

وفقنا الله جميعاً لما فيه خير الوطن

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أهداف المؤتمر

تسليط الضوء على أهمية البحث العلمي في مجال التقنيات الحيوية في خدمة المجتمع

التعرف على أحدث البحوث العلمية واستعراض النماذج الرائدة في العلوم الطبية والزراعية والبيئية

إستعراض التحديات التي تواجه توظيف التقنيات الحيوية في خدمة المجتمع وسبل معالجتها

العمل على توطين إستخدام التقنية الحيوية في مؤسسات التعليم العالي

توثيق وتعزيز جسور التعاون بين الباحث الليبيين والإقليميين في هذا المجال

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المحور الطبي :

- الأمرض الوراثةة والجينية
- علم الوراثة الوبائي والجزيئي
- الميكروبائ الممرضة ومكافحة العدوى
- الخلايا الجذعية وتطبيقاتها
- الأخلاقيات البيولوجية في مجال التطبيقات الحيوية

المحور الزراعي :

- تحسين خصائص النباتات باستخدام التقنيات الحيوية
- الاكثار الدقيق للنباتات النادرة والمهددة بالانقراض
- تحسين الإنتاج الزراعي الحيواني وحفظ الأصول الوراثةة
- الزراعات المائية والهوائية
- إستخلاص وإنتاج المواد الفعالة من موارد طبيعية

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- التلو؁ البيئي وإدارة المخلفات
- المعالجة الحيوية
- إنتاج الوقود الحيوي
- الوعي البيئي

المتحدثون الرئيسيون

Environmental Biotechnology and Sustainability

An experienced qualified water, and environment specialist, with over 40years' experience in consultancy, management, research, teaching and training in the UK and Overseas. Established international training, growing research and technology links. Currently working as Researcher Consultant for Centre of Excellence in Environmental Studies, King Abdulaziz University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Mohamed Elfleet
malfleet@kau.edu.sa

Wellness Promotion Through (Bio)Technology

Professor Abdelbaset Buhmeida, MD, PhD, boasts over 25 years of experience in cancer research and biobanking, establishing himself as a prominent figure in the field. While renowned for his expertise in molecular profiling and personalized medicine, he has recently redirected his efforts towards championing wellness sciences. Engaging in initiatives to promote wellness and foster the growth of the wellness industry, Prof. Buhmeida leverages his extensive knowledge to bridge conventional medical practices with holistic wellness approaches for the betterment of individuals and communities.

Abdelbaset Buhmeida
abuhme@utu.fi

Characterizing the role of genetic variants in disease, from rare diseases to cancer and neurodegeneration: the importance of a worldwide approach

Emanuele Buratti is currently Group Leader of the Molecular Pathology Lab at the International Centre for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology (ICGEB) in Trieste and professor at the University of Trieste. Previously, he studied at the University of Trieste for a M.Sc. in Biology and a Ph.D. in Biochemistry. In 1995, he moved to ICGEB (www.icgeb.org) as a Staff Research Scientist and is currently leading the Molecular Pathology lab. Dr. Buratti principal areas of expertise are the investigation of RNA binding proteins and RNA metabolism in neurodegeneration and metabolic diseases. On these subjects, Emanuele Buratti is the author of more than 200 research papers mostly focusing on the impact of disease-associated mutations on the RNA splicing process and the role played by TDP-43 in Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) and Frontotemporal Dementia (FTD).

Emanuele Buratti

Emanuele.Buratti@icgeb.org

[Homepage:](#)

<http://www.icgeb.trieste.it/molecular-pathology.html>

العروض التقديمية

Oral Presentation

7-2456 MO

المحور الطبي

Nutritional value of *Arum cyrenaicum* Hurbycorms

Laila Ben Ramadan¹, Rabeeah Altarhouni¹, Abdurzag Zwawi², Mabroka Algriani³
and Abdurzag Auzi⁴

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research
Center, Tripoli, Libya

3. Food and Drug Censorship Center-
Tripoli-Libya.

2. Faculty of Medicine, Tripoli
University-Tripoli, Libya

4. Faculty of Pharmacy, Tripoli
University-Tripoli, Libya

lailabenramadan18@gmail.com

Abstract

The objective of this study to present the nutritional values and food security importance of *Arum cyrenaicum*, which belongs to Araceae family cultivated for its edible corms in Aljable-aAlkhdar-Libya and used as a staple food. Nutritionally, *Arum Cyrenaica* corms were found to be rich in protein (7.19%) and low amount of fat (0.29%) in a dry form. *Arum cyrenaicum* contains fairly high amount of ash; total (4.13%) From which it can be inferred it contain good mineral contents.

Results indicated this plant is excellent sources of minerals particularly of sodium, calcium, iron, copper, zinc, and phosphorus; 46.3, 1.39, 2.9, 3.4, 4.72, and 0.18 respectively. Now a day, zinc deficiency is widespread and affects the health and well-being of populations worldwide and since of *Arum cyrenaicum* is one of the few nonanimal sources of zinc, *A. cyrenaicum* with adequate zinc content is beneficial in promoting healthy aging is particularly important as it

prevents neoplastic cell growth is involved in mitotic cell division, DNA and RNA repair and improve immunity. Corms could be deactivated covid-19 due to investigate good amount of copper and zinc.

Keywords: Arum cyrenaicum, Nutrition, Araceae.

7-2427 MO

المحور الطبي

Isolation and Analysis of Plasmid-Linked Antibiotic Resistance and Biofilm Formation in Gram-negative Bacteria from Diabetic Foot Ulcer Patients in Sebha Medical Facilities

Warda Khalifa¹ , *Shamsi Saad Shamsi^{2 3} , Khadija Ahmed⁴ , Habeeb Aboubaker¹
, Khalid rehoumah¹

1. Department of Biotechnology,
Faculty of Science, Sebha University,
Sebha, Libya

3. Department of Microbiology, Libyan
Medical Research Center, Sebha , Libya
Food and Drug Censorship Center
Tripoli-Libya.

2. Department of Botany, Faculty of
Science, Sebha University, Sebha, Libya

4. Department of Microbiology, Faculty
of Medicin, Sebha, Libya

sha.saad@sebhau.edu.ly

Abstract

Severe diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) in patients from various medical Centres in Sebha were the focus of this study, which examined the prevalence, biofilm formation, and antibiotic resistance mechanisms of Gram-negative bacteria. Analysis of swabs and deep tissue samples from 27 patients, The cross-sectional analysis of samples from DFU patients reveals a significant predominance of *Enterobacter cloacae* (47.61%) and *Klebsiella pneumonia* (35.71%). Both exhibit high extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL) production levels and resistance to key antibiotics like ceftazidime and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid. Additionally, the study uncovers the substantial biofilm formation capabilities with a high level of biofilm production of *Enterobacter cloacae* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, compounding treatment challenges. A notable correlation between plasmid presence and antibiotic resistance, particularly to Gentamicin, is

demonstrated, underscoring the need for innovative treatment strategies. The findings call for heightened surveillance and tailored therapeutic approaches in the management of DFUs.

Keywords: Gram-negative bacteria-Diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs)-Antibiotic resistance-Biofilm formation-Plasmid content correlation.

7-2487 MO

المحور الطبي

**Investigating the Efficacy of Plant Extract-Infused Nanoparticles in
Detecting and Eliminating Bacterial Contamination in *Juniperus
Phoenicia* Plant Tissue Culture**

Hajer Elfowiris ^{1*}, Rafa I Mohammad¹

1.Libyan Biotechnology Research Centre,Albayda,Libya

hajer0309@gmail.com

Abstract

Preventing or avoiding microbial contamination of plant tissue cultures is critical to successful micropropagation. Epiphytic and endophytic organisms can cause severe losses to micro-propagated plants at each stage of growth. Noble metal nanoparticles loaded smart polymer microgels have gained much attention due to fascinating combination of their properties in a single system. These hybrid systems have been extensively used in biomedicines, photonics, and agriculture. In this study, the epiphytic bacterial contamination of *Juniperus Phoenicia* were detected using biochemical tests. The biosynthesis of AgNPs was carried out by the volume ratio of the extract and AgNO₃ 9:1 in reaction time 12 hours, the concentration is 1mM solution and the plant extracts were prepared using the leaves of dried thyme, thapsia and milius, the extracts were obtained through boiling technique. The results have shown contamination with *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella*. When treated with extracts, Milius showed the greatest activity against *Klebsiella* as the zone is 3.5, thymus showed antibacterial activity against both *E. coli* with a zone of 2.95 and 2.95 against

Pseudomonas aeruginosa, the lowest antibacterial action was achieved by Thapsia with a range from 1.3 to 1.7, respectively.

Keywords: Nanoparticles, Juniperus Phoenicia, Thapsia, Milius, thymus, Antibacterial .

7-2401 MO

المحور الطبي

Characterization of Multidrug Resistance Enterobacteriaceae Isolates from Hospitalized Patients in Tripoli, Libya

Nada Elgriw, Véronique Métayer, Antoine Drapeau, Pauline François, Sana Azaiez, Maha Mestouri, Hajer Rhim, Adam Elzagheid, Najeeb Soufiyah, Jean-Yves Madec, Cherifa Chaouch, Wejdene Mansour and Marisa Haenni

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.
2. Faculty of pharmacy Monastir, Doctoral commission in Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Monastir, Monastir 5000, Tunisia.
3. Laboratory of Transmissible Diseases and Biologically Active Substances LR99ES27, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Monastir, Monastir 5000, Tunisia.
Unité Antibiorésistance et Virulence Bactériennes, ANSES – Université de Lyon 69007 Lyon, France aboratoire de Recherche Biophysique

nadaelgriw@gmail.com

Abstract

Introduction, the emergence of multidrug resistance in Gram-negative bacilli (GNB) now represents a daily issue for the management of antimicrobial therapy in intensive care unit (ICU) patients. Emerging resistance in Enterobacteriaceae is a significant problem that instantly need immediate attention. Resistance to extended-spectrum cephalosprins (ESC) and carbapenems in Enterobacterales are major issues in public health. Carbapenem-resistance in particular is associated with increased morbidity and mortality. Moreover, such resistances are often co-harbored with resistances to non-beta-lactam antibiotics, and pathogens quickly become multi-drug resistant (MDR).

Only few studies were published on antimicrobial resistance in Libyan hospitals, but all reported worri some results.

Materials and methods, we studied 54 multi-drug resistant (MDR) isolates that were collected from 49 patients at the Tripoli University Hospital between 2019 and 2021. They were characterized using phenotypic methods, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and pulse field gel electrophoresis (PFGE), and a sub-set of isolates were short- and long-read whole-genome sequenced.

Results and conclusion showed that the burden of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) was mainly due to *K. pneumoniae* (49/54), twenty-six patients were females (26/49, 53.1%) and 17 were males (34.6%) and all isolates displayed resistances to several families of beta-lactams, including to carbapenems in 65.3% of the *K. pneumoniae* isolates and 40.0% of the *E. coli* isolates, which were conferred by the presence of at least one beta-lactam resistance gene and colistin-resistance which done via broth dilution were observed in 12 of 49 *K. pneumoniae* isolates and that several high-risk clones were responsible for the spread of these isolates, namely ST11, ST17, ST101, and ST147. ESC- and carbapenem resistance was due to a wide variety of enzymes (CTX-M, OXA-48, NDM, KPC), with their corresponding genes carried by different plasmids, including IncF-IncHI2 and IncF-IncR hybrids. This study highlights that implementation of infection prevention, control and surveillance measures are urgently needed in Libya to fight against antimicrobial resistance.

Keywords: carbapenem; amikacin; colistin; *K. pneumoniae*; *E. coli*; nosocomial infection; NDM-1; OXA-48; KPC-1.

7-2465 MO

المحور الطبي

Effect of the Active Substances in Biocidal Products on Antibiotic Resistance of Gram-Negative Bacteria

¹Nadia. E. Al-Abdli, ¹Amal Boulifa

1. MSc of Microbiology; Laboratory Dept., eye Hospital, Benghazi

batul.gr155@gmail.com

Abstract

Intensified cleaning protocols during the COVID-19 pandemic specifically call for the increased use of chemical disinfectants routinely used in community environments, as one effective measure to contain the virus spread. An underappreciated risk, however, is that the persisting input of chemical disinfectants can exacerbate the growth of biocide tolerant and antibiotic-resistant bacteria. The aim of this study was to assess the effect of exposure of antibiotic-susceptible Gram-negative bacteria isolates to sub-inhibitory concentrations of biocides.

Methods: Twenty clinical antibiotic-susceptible Gram-negative bacteria were isolated (obtained from clinical specimens from all of the Aljala hospital, Benghazi, Libya units) were identified by standard conventional microbiological and biochemical methods at microbiology laboratory of hospital. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of some products were revealed. Antimicrobial susceptibility was performed with antibiotics used for the therapy of the tested isolates before and after exposure to sub-inhibitory concentrations of biocides (sub-MICs).

Result: Gram-negative bacteria exhibited an acquired tolerance to biocides and an increase in antibiotic resistance after exposure to sub-MICs of biocides, except two isolates of *E. coli*. *P. aeruginosa* and *A. baumannii* isolates showed greater tolerance for all biocides tested. **Conclusions:** Vast use of disinfectants in various environments and their accumulation represents a potential risk for selective pressure towards selection of bacteria with decreased antibiotic susceptibility.

Keywords: Gram-negative bacteria, MDR bacteria, MIC; MBC, Sub-minimum inhibitory; Biocides tolerant.

7-24108 MO

المحور الطبي

Resistance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and other nosocomial pathogens to popular disinfectants at Benghazi medical center (BMC), Libya.

Siham Rajab Agouri¹, Suad Abdullah Ajaj², Asma Elramli^{2, 3},
and Fawzya Ali Muftah Elmajbri⁴

1. Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Sciences, Benghazi University, Benghazi, Libya.
2. Department of Medical Technology, College of Science and Technology - Qaminis, Benghazi, Libya.
3. Alakeed Laboratory
4. Reference medical laboratory

SihamRAgouri2019@gmail.com

Abstract

Resistance to antibiotics and disinfectants in various bacterial strains is a major public health problem in the world. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* as an opportunistic pathogen that cause nosocomial infections particularly isolates high levels of antibiotic resistance. Antimicrobial disinfectants are used as primary treatment options against pathogens on surfaces in healthcare facilities. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of five used disinfectants in Benghazi medical center hospital.

Methods: This study was carried out during in the period from 1st of Mars 2019 to end of April 2019. The bactericidal efficacy of five disinfectant products (alcohol, iodine, hydrogen peroxide, surfanios and glutaraldehyde) was tested against 60 samples isolated bacteria from health care workers hands, medical wards, floors and equipment. All isolates were grown in 9 ml of broth media mixed with 1 ml from each disinfectant then all cultures leave for 2.5 mins and 5 mins at room temperature ,after that inoculated on nutrient agar and

MacConkey agar then, all plates were incubated at 37°C /overnight . Bactericidal efficacy was determined by detection the colonies. The effect of antibiotics susceptibility test was carried out by disk diffusion method. **Results:** All isolated bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Micrococcus spp* and *Klebsiella pneumonia*) were identified by microbiological characteristics and biochemical tests. Antibiotic resistance profiles were observed. The study revealed that tested disinfectants (hydrogen peroxide, glutaraldehyde, alcohol and iodine) had high bactericidal efficacies on tested isolates. However, *P. aeruginosa* did not effected with hydrogen peroxide and alcohol and the methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* grew on iodine containing medium.

Conclusion: The appropriate disinfectant (or chemical sterilants) must be selected correctly, After it testing if it has efficiency against microbial agents or does not to avoid any dissemination of disinfectants resistance bacteria, also antibiotics resistance bacteria in hospitals environments must be detected.

Keywords: Disinfectant, Efficacy, bactericidal, *P. aeruginosa* .

7-2425 MO

المحور الطبي

Spatiotemporal Distribution of Case Fatality Rate of the Coronavirus 2019 Disease (COVID-19) in Libya

Abdusalam Sharef Mahmoud^{1*}, Hafsa A. Alemam², Ahlam Masaud Ellafi¹, Mouna A. Abdunnabi¹, Ahmed. A. Zaghdani², Salah Edin El Meshri², Adam Elzghied^{2,3}

1. University of Tripoli, Tripoli, Libya
2. Libyan Biotechnology Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.
3. University of Benghazi, Benghazi, Libya

Abd.mahmoud@uot.edu.ly

Abstract

Background: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 is the respiratory disease responsible for the COVID-19 pandemic; one of the worst pandemics reported throughout human history with a high Case fatality rate reported leading to high potential impacts and lockdown of the entire world's activities.

Objective: This study was undertaken to assess and determine the Case fatality rate of COVID-19 and its associated risk factors among the Libyan population.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective cohort study involving 1,000 random nasal swabs from Libya between July 2020 and January 2021 examined the presence of coronavirus antigens in samples from different regions and sexes using a real-time reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain-reaction assay at the Libyan Centre for Biotechnology, Tripoli, Libya.

Results: The overall case fatality rate was estimated to be (4.7%; 3.37%-5.99%) with a 95% confidence interval (CI).

The highest Case fatality rate (40.78%; 95% CI = 29.74%-51.84%) was reported among the elderly age group. The Case fatality rate among the different age groups was statistically significant ($p = .00001$). The highest and lowest Case fatality rate were estimated to be (5.04%; 95% CI = 3.57%-6.51%) and (4.48%; 95% = 0.00%-9.43%) in the western and middle regions, respectively; however, there was no statistical difference ($p = .4$) between the regions. **Conclusions:** The study found a high Case fatality rate of COVID-19 among Libyans, with flattened curve patterns but uneven distribution. Age-related factors significantly influenced the case fatality rate, with the elderly reporting higher rates

Keywords: COVID-19, Case Fatality Rate, Spatiotemporal, Libya.

7-2492 MO

المحور الطبي

Genetic Disorders in Libya: The Situation and The Hope from Physicians' Perspectives – A Pilot Study

Takwa Murad Shlaki¹, Maram Fathi Ftis¹, Nehal Omar Alhamisi¹,
Lidya Ramadan Benhussin¹, Maram Murad Dhan¹, Ahmad M. Ramadan²

1. Libyan Medical Research Center - Zuwara, Zuwara, Libya

2. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

ahmad.ramaddann@gmail.com

Abstract

Genetic disorders pose a significant public health challenge in Libya, with their prevalence potentially elevated by consanguineous marriages. Unfortunately, there is a lack of understanding about the epidemiology and impacts of these diseases in the country, and the studies about the subject are scarce and outdated. To reduce this gap, we aim to survey physicians experienced with genetic disorders in Libya. Our procedure involves a mixed-methods approach that combines quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis.

Through this approach, we intend to gain insights into the epidemiology, impact, and documentation system. Additionally, we assess the current needs and future initiatives for research and practice in this field. The findings of this pilot study provide valuable insights into the current status and future directions for genetic disorders research and practice. These insights inform the design and implementation of a larger-scale study that covers different regions and stakeholders throughout the country.

7-2437 MO

المحور الطبي

Prevalence of vaginal infection and Candidiasis among pregnant and non-pregnant women in Libya

Yosra Lamami¹, Mwada Jallul¹, Samira Al dwegin¹, Mohamed Milad¹, Abdulbaset Abozwida¹, Ahmed Zaghdani¹

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli, Libya.

yosralamami@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Vaginal infections are a major associated health problems that consequently leads to serious complications, this study aimed to determine the prevalence of bacteria and fungi responsible for vaginosis (BV), among pregnant and non-pregnant women in Tripoli, Libya and associated risk factors.

Materials and Methods: A total 160 Libyan females from Tripoli, Libya were participated in this study. Socio-demographic and clinical data were recorded. Vaginal swabs were collected from both pregnant and non-pregnant women with symptoms of vaginal infection, examined microscopically and microbiologically for BV and Candida.

Results: Candida infection was prevalent among pregnant women (50.0 %), *E. coli* was more prevalent among non-pregnant women (25.6%), *E. coli* showed higher resistance to all antibiotic with 100% resistance for amoxicillin and Cephalixin, compared to *Staphylococcus* isolates.

Conclusion: Microbial infection was very common among non-pregnant women complaining of pruritus, burning, and/or vaginal discharge. *Candida*, *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus* were the most frequently encountered organisms. Resistance of *E. coli* to antibiotics was very prevalent.

Keywords: vaginal infection, Bacteria, *Candida*, antibiotic resistance, Libya.

7-2490 MO

Opnm

Moringa Oleifera's Protective Effect Against DNA Damage from Hydroxychloroquinennmm

.,Wafaa Younis Mohammed Abdulsalambb

1. Faculty of Medical Technology, Sebha University, Libya.

wa.abdussalam@sebhau.edu.ly

Abstract

The purpose of this study to evaluate whether powdered *Moringa oleifera* leaves could shield DNA from hydroxychloroquine-induced damage, male albino rats were utilized. They were given dry moringa leaf powder with lunch for three weeks. Additionally, they were administered hydroxychloroquine at various doses every day for five days. Malondialdehyde (MDA) has been detected in serum. In addition to superoxide dismutase (SOD) enzyme measurement, the Comet test or single cell gel electrophoresis (SCGE) method were employed to evaluate for DNA damage in the liver. MDA increased while SOD dropped otherwise. After being treated with powdered *Moringa oleifera* leaf, the activity of antioxidant factors was raised and the MDA level and were decreased. These findings suggest that the liver is a key target organ and that hydroxychloroquine is genotoxic at the levels used. *M. oleifera* demonstrated moderate DNA damage and a protective function against HCQ-induced DNA damage.

Keywords: Moringa oleifera, DNA, antioxidant, Hydroxychloroquine.

7-2499 MO

المحور الطبي

Biosynthesis and Characterisation of Silver Nanoparticles Using *Ajucaive* leaf extract and Their Antibacterial Activity Assessment

Mariam Mohammed Sasi, Samira Omar Hribesh* and Rabia Omar Eshkourfu
Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science , Elmergib University, Al-Khums

samira.hribesh@elmergib.edu.ly

Abstract

Synthesis of silver nanoparticles from plant extracts have been widely using in the field of medicine, particularly as antibacterial agents. In present study, *Ajucaive* leaf extract was performed using aqueous solution that was tested for its phytochemical components. The results of phytochemical analysis of *Ajucaive* leaf extract had alkaloids, carbohydrate, proteins, flavonoids, phenols, saponins and coumarins. Synthesis of silver nanoparticles was performed using *Ajucaive* leaf extract with 1 mM solution of silver nitrate . The synthesised silver nanoparticles was characterized with UV-Vis spectroscopy, X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), and Fourier Transform Infra-Red (FTIR) spectrum. SEM analysis revealed the size of the AgNPs of 36 nm, 55 nm, 70 nm and 100 nm. EDX study appeared the optical absorption peak was detected at 3 keV, which is the characteristic peak for the absorbed metallic silver nanoparticles. FTIR analysis identified the possible functional group involved in the reduction of silver metal ions into silver nanoparticles. In addition, the antibacterial activity of synthesized silver nanoparticles was also examined and the results showed good antibacterial activities against *E. coli* and *Streptococcus* bacteria.

7-24123 MO

المحور الطبي

Prevalence of Iron Deficiency Anemia and its Risk Factors among Libyan Biotechnology Research Center (BTRC) Workers.

Asma Alboeshi¹, Mohamed Broom¹, Saber Dalyom¹, Faihaa Omran¹, Sundus alshileeb¹, Warda Haroush¹, Salah Tabal¹, Farag Eltaib¹, Fawzi Ebrahim^{1*}

1., Libyan Biotechnology Research Center (LBTRC), Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

Fawzi.Omer@yahoo.com

Abstract

Background: Globally, iron deficiency is known to be the most common nutritional disorder. About 50 % of the world's population was estimated to suffer from anemia.

Objective: This study carried out to determine the prevalence of iron deficiency anemia (IDA) and evaluate its risk factors for male and female employees at Libyan biotech--nology research center in Tripoli, Libya.

Material and Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted between June and August 2023, overall 201 participants 67 male and 134 female aged (4 –74 years) on the BTRC employees and their families'. Interviewed and sample collected. Anemia was classified according to WHO criteria. Independent t-tests, Proportions, chi-square test and regression were applied to assess the factors associated with anemia and p value less than 0.01 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The mean (\pm SD) age of the study population was 38.35 ± 13.97 years, 33 % of study participants were male and 67 % were female. The overall prevalence of IDA in the current study was 34 % (13 % in males and 87% in females) which is a higher prevalence rates in women compared to men. ($P < 0.001$). Similarly, the mean of hematological parameters, Serum ferritin, Serum iron , and total Iron Capacity for IDA male and female participants had significantly level ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, the incidence of IDA was decreasing with advancing of participants age, the frequent consumption of tea (69 .6%), coffee (60.4%) and cola (75.4%) and family history of IDA (29.4%) were found to be common risk and a significant factors associated with IDA among a study sample ($P < 0.001$).

Conclusion: the prevalence of IDA was moderately high among the study sample (34 %), a higher rates of IDA were observed among female (87%) compared to male (13%), the harmful effect on iron absorption as a frequent consumption of tea , coffee and cola , due to its high polyphenol (tannins) content, which inhibits nonheme iron absorption .

Keywords: Iron deficiency anemia, serum ferritin, serum iron, Total Iron binding capacity.

7-24124 MO

المحور الطبي

Economic, Simple Protocol for Amniotic Membrane Graft Preparation

Samira Aldwegin,, Ellafi Elbahri, Mohamed Milad, Sedigh Bshir, Adel Mabrouk,
Mohamed Bream, Yosra Lamami, Fawzi Ebrahim,

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

Fawzi.Omer@yahoo.com

Abstract

The Human Amniotic membrane (HAM) is the inner part of the placenta provide the fetus protective and nutritional roles for the fetus during pregnancy. It contains numerous growth elements and proteins that mediate unique regenerative properties and increase wound healing in tissue regeneration. HAM were harvested at Libyan Biotechnology Research Centre (LCBTR) from the placenta of healthy women delivered by cesarean section. The mothers were screened for hepatitis B and C, HIV and syphilis, and their consent for the use of their placenta was obtained post permission from local bioethics committee. HAM is prepared under sterile conditions, washed with balanced salt solution containing penicillin, streptomycin, neomycin and amphotericin B, placed in tissue culture and glycerol at a ratio of 1:1. The selection of HAM grafts for bioburden test and verification of sterilization was conducted randomly from the HAM grafts routinely processed during (2022-2023) against aerobic and anaerobic bacteria yeast and molds. Bioburden load was determined according to ISO 11737-1 by using bacterial media of Trypton soya broth incubation at temperature and time, 34 °C and 14 days, respectively. Thioglycolate broth for total an- aerobic bacteria incubated in anaerobic gar at 34 °C for 5 days.

Sterility and quality of the HAM products is carried out based on the quality management system at the tissue lab. Thereby in our center (LBTRC) we successfully obtained the bioproduct from placenta free from infectious agents to use in several medical applications .

Keywords: Amniotic membrane, ulcers, lyophilisation, radiation sterilisation, Caesarean section, cryopreserved, ophthalmic, amniotic membrane grafts, amniotic membrane preservation, air drying, radiation sterilisation.

7-24130 MO

المحور الطبي

Assessment of Atherogenic Risk Indices and Dyslipidemia in Libyan Smokers

Hafsa A. ALEMAM¹, Arij M. MUSTAFA^{1*}, Afaf SHEBANI¹, Marwa ATTAYEB¹, Abdurrahmn A. AkAREM¹, Adam I. ELZAGHEID¹ and Farag I. ELTAIB¹

1.Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.
afafashibane@gmail.com

Abstract

Background/aim: The atherogenic index of plasma (AIP) is a novel indicator for assessing the risk of atherogenicity and cardiometabolic health. The study aimed to assess the lipid profile and atherogenic indices, including the novel indicator of AIP, in Libyan smokers, given its association with a greater frequency of major adverse cardiovascular events in patients at risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD).

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted at the Libyan Biotechnology Research Centre in Tripoli, Libya. Two hundred Libyan male subjects were divided into two groups: a group of smokers and a group of non-smokers (as the control group). After an overnight 12-hour fast, five millilitres of fasting whole blood were collected for analysis. Plasma lipid profiles, including total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TAG), lowdensity lipoprotein (LDL), and high-density lipoprotein (HDL), were assessed, and levels of atherogenic index of plasma (AIP) were determined.

Results: All 200 participants, including both smokers and non-smokers, were residents of Tripoli. The study revealed elevated levels of total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TGs), and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) in the smokers' group, which were significantly higher compared to the non-smokers. Interestingly, all smoker participants exhibited AIP levels greater than 0.1, indicating an increased risk of atherogenicity. In contrast, only 15% of the control group had AIP levels indicating intermediate risk, while the remaining 85% had low risk.

Conclusion: There is a significant association between smoking and atherogenic indexes. In situations where all atherogenic parameters are normal, AIP may be the alternative screening tool.

Keywords: Atherogenic index of plasma, cardiovascular disease, high-density lipoprotein, low-density lipoprotein, triglycerides.

7-24132 MO

المحور الطبي

Knowledge and attitudes towards premarital screening programs among students at the University of Tripoli, Libya

Afaf Shebani, Ariej M. Mustafa, Halla Elshwekh, Inas M Alhudiri,
Abduladim Hmmier

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

afafabdljuad84@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Despite the increase in hereditary diseases in Arab countries due to the high rates of consanguineous marriages, research on community awareness of premarital screening (PMS) for disease carriers is still scarce.

Aim: To investigate knowledge and attitudes towards genetic PMS programs among university students in Libya.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was carried out using a self-administered questionnaire distributed to 400 Libyan students aged 18-25 years at the University of Tripoli.

Results: Most of the participants (79%) agreed that a PMS program is important and expressed willingness to have PMS if they were advised to do so. Two-thirds of the participants (67%) had heard of PMS programs, of whom 27.2% heard of them from the social media.

Conclusion: Most of the university students had good knowledge of PMS but poor knowledge of the hereditary diseases targeted by PMS. Most of them had a positive attitude towards PMS.

Keywords: consanguineous marriage, premarital screening, hereditary diseases, knowledge, attitudes, Libya.

7-2439 MO

المحور الطبي

Investigation of humoral immune response for SARS-COV-2 in cancer patients

Safa Alshen¹, Inas Alhudiri^{2*}, Afaf Abushaala, Yosra Lamami², Fawzi Ebrahim²,
Salah Tabal², Adam Elzagheid²

1. Department of Al Hani Health Center, Tripoli Health Services, Tripoli, Libya.

2. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya..

inas.alhudiri@btc.org.ly

Abstract

Background cancer patients face a doubled mortality rate from SARS-CoV-2 compared to the general population. This increased vulnerability arises from the immunocompromised state induced by various cancer treatments, elevating the risk of severe COVID-19

Objective: To measure the levels of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibodies in cancer patients after COVID-19 vaccination or infection and examine different cancer treatments.

Methods: This study included 304 patients with different cancer types and 131 healthy people. Patients were tested for anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibodies after receiving one, two, or three doses of the COVID-19 vaccine or after COVID-19 infection.

Results: About 56% of vaccinated patients who had no previous COVID-19 infection had high seropositivity IgG. and 76.4% of vaccinated patients with previous COVID-19 had high seropositivity IgG. These results revealed a statistically significant difference in immune response ($p = 0.001$). Antibody levels were similar in cancer patients compared with healthy people who received two doses of the vaccine duration less than 180 day. There was no significant difference between homologous and heterologous vaccination strategies.

7-24131 MO

المحور الطبي

INvestigation of Humoral Immune Response to SARS-COV-2 Following Infection and After Vaccination in Chronic Dialysis Patients in Tripoli, Libya

Somaya Alkafi¹, Inas Alhudiri^{2*}, Yosra Lamami², Fawzi Ebrahim², Salah Tabal², Adam Elzagheid²

1. Al-jehad Health Center, Tripoli, Libya.
2. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

inas.alhudiri@btc.org.ly

Abstract

Background: People on haemodialysis (HD) are at higher risk of severe illness from COVID-19. Their immune response to infections may be weak and may have an attenuated response to vaccines.

Objective: To measure the levels of anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibodies in HD patients after COVID-19 vaccination or infection.

Methods: This study included 294 HD patients and 76 healthy people. Patients were tested for anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgG antibodies after receiving one, two, or three doses of the COVID-19 vaccine or after COVID-19 infection.

Results: Antibodies were detected in 71.7% of vaccinated patients who received their last dose within the past 180 days. Of these patients, 34% had previously been infected with COVID-19. The majority of vaccinated patients who had not been infected with COVID-19 had positive antibody levels.

Antibody levels were similar in HD patients compared with healthy people who received two doses of the vaccine. There was no significant difference between homologous and heterologous vaccination strategies.

Conclusion: HD patients generally mounted a good humoral immune response to COVID-19 vaccination, with antibody levels comparable to healthy individuals vaccinated with two doses. This response was seen whether previously infected with COVID-19 or not. However, antibody levels were higher in previously infected patients.

Keywords: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; Vaccine; homologous; dialysis; Beckman Coulter Access

7-24135 MO

المحور الطبي

Analysis of BRCA1 Germline Variants in Breast Cancer Families from Libya

Eanas Elmaihub^{1, 2*}, Inas Alhudiri³, Ahmad M. Ramadan³, Mouna Eljilani³, Adam Elzagheid³, Fakraia Elfagi⁴ and Elham Hassen^{1,5}

1. Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Monastir, Department of Molecular Biology, Monastir University, Monastir, Tunisia
2. Laboratory of Molecular Biology, Faculty of Sciences, Molecular Biology and Biochemistry Department, Sabratha University, Sabratha, Libya.
3. Libyan Biotechnology Research Centre, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya. Tripoli, Libya.
4. Department of Oncology, National Cancer Institute, Sabratha, Libya
5. Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Monastir, Department of Molecular Biology, 18 Monastir University, Monastir, Tunisia

einasse@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Breast cancer is the leading cause of cancer mortality in women in Libya. *BRCA1* 25 variants differ globally, reflecting the genetic diversity and evolutionary history of 26 various populations. However, the exact distribution and impact of these variants and 27 data on their prevalence and clinical significance have not been fully studied. The role 28 of *BRCA1* germline variants on hereditary breast cancer in Libyan population remains 29 largely unexplored. Our study aims to investigate the characteristics and frequency of 30 *BRCA1* variants in exons 5, 11, and 20 among Libyan breast cancer families.

Patients and Methods: Out of 36 selected cases belonging to 33 families, twenty (18 breast cancer women and two unaffected relatives belonging to two families) were screened for *BRCA1* exons for *BRCA1* exons 5, 11, and 20 using Sanger sequencing during the period from 2018 to 2020 at the National Cancer Institute, Sabratha, Libya. The proband of each family had completed an epidemiology and family history questionnaire.

Results: Twenty-seven variants, all in exon 11 except one in exon 20 with a minor allele frequency below 0.01, were detected in 10 unrelated families with a frequency of 55.6% (10/18). Of the 27 variants, 22 (81.5%) were heterozygous alleles, four variants appeared both homozygous in some patients and heterozygous in others. A frameshift pathogenic variant, c.2643del, and one novel variant allele c.1366A>G were identified. Furthermore, seven other variants with unknown clinical significance were detected. The variants include c.1158T>A, c.1346C>G, c.1174C>G, c.3630G>T, c.3599A>T, and c.3400G>C in exon 11, and c.5244T>A in exon 20. Six variants with conflicting interpretations of pathogenicity, c. 3460T>A, c. 3572G>A, c. 3700G>C, c. 1246C>G, c. 1344C>G, and c. 1054G>A, were also identified. Additionally, we found 12 benign or likely benign variants.

Conclusion: The *BRCA1* variants found in Libyan population were rare and had not been reported in North African patients. These findings provide preliminary insights into the *BRCA1* variants potentially involved in hereditary breast cancer within the Libyan population. Further functional, computational, and population-based analysis is essential to determine their significance and elucidate their potential impact on the risk of developing breast cancer, ultimately leading to more personalized management strategies.

Keywords: BRCA1, breast cancer, genetic variants, hereditary breast cancer, Libya.

7-24142 MO

المحور الطبي

Screening of BRCA1 Variants in Libyan Breast Cancer Patients

Halla H. Elshwekh¹, [Hamza M. Abduljalil](#)¹, Abdul Nasser A. Mohammed¹, Inas M. Alhudiri¹, Mouna M. ElJilani¹, Ahmed A. Ramadan¹, Ahmad Elkikli¹, Ariej M. Mustafa¹, Naji Jornaz², Nour Eldeen Aribi³, Adam Elzagheid¹, Nabil Enattah^{1*}

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.
2. Department of Oncology, Tripoli University Hospital, Tripoli, Libya.
3. Department of General Surgery, Tripoli Central Hospital, Tripoli, Libya.

nabil.enattah@yahoo.com

Abstract

Background: The majority of hereditary breast cancer is associated with genetic mutations in breast cancer type 1 and 2 susceptibility genes (BRCA1 and BRCA2).

Aim: Screening of exons 2, 5, 8,9,11,10,13,18 and 20 of BRCA1 gene in Libyan breast cancer patients.

Methods: 48 samples were collected from patients with family history of breast cancer and were genetically analyzed by Sanger sequencing.

Results:

Genetic analysis revealed 17 variants in the BRCA1 gene, distributed across exons 2, 5, 8, 9, 10, and 18. Exon 10 had 3 novel mutations (c.1019>C, c.2363T>G, c.3192T>C) alongside 6 unclassified and 3 benign variants.

Conclusion:

The study identified a variety of genetic variants in the BRCA1 gene of Libyan breast cancer patients with a family history of the disease, including three novel mutations in exon 10. While some of the identified variants were classified as benign, several remained unclassified, requiring further investigation to determine their clinical significance and potential role in breast cancer development.

Keywords: genetic variants, breast cancer, unclassified variants, Libyan.

7-24122 MO

المحور الطبي

**Chromosome (8) pericentric inversion and recurrent pregnancy loss:
Case study**

Ibrahim A. Teka¹ & Laila M. Alfageih²

1.Libyan National Infertility Project & Faculty of Medical Technology – Misurata

2. Department of Medical Science / Faculty of Dentistry / Tobrouk University

teka42@hotmail.com

Abstract

Recurrent pregnancy loss (RPL) or Recurrent miscarriage (RM) can be defined as three or more consecutive pregnancy losses before 24 weeks of gestation. Many studies have proven that parental chromosomal abnormalities represent an important etiology of RM. This case of study was run to identify the role of chromosome rearrangement in RPL. To achieve the aim, a case of a phenotypically and normal physical examinations healthy couple, were subjected to cytogenetic analysis apparently after experiencing three RPLs. In their past the investigations were only limited to physical, imaging and routine laboratory testing in which no abnormal values were ever reported. Herein, the cytogenetic tests using G-banding showed that the wife was a carrier of pericentric inversion on chromosome 8; precisely 46,XX inv (8) (p11;q23), estimating the possible origin of the multiple pregnancy loss in this case. This finding underlies the importance of cytogenetic investigations in the routine management of RPL.

المصقات

Posters

7-2486 MP

المحور الطبي

Antimicrobial Resistance Pattern of Clinically Isolated Strains of *Acinetobacter baumannii* in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Libya

Dalal Thwood¹, Zynab elgadiym¹

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

thwood@btc.org.ly

Abstract

Acinetobacter baumannii (*A. baumannii*) is an opportunistic pathogen responsible for a significant proportion of hospital-associated infections. Its high prevalence of resistance to many classes of antibiotics makes treatment challenging. This cross-sectional study was conducted retrospectively in the Department of Microbiology at Tripoli University Hospital in Libya from January to June 2021. The identification of the isolates, we analyzed, were accomplished by VITEK® 2 (bioMérieux, France) automated system and the isolates were labelled as susceptible, intermediate susceptible and resistant based on minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC). A total of 86 *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolates were obtained from various clinical specimens. The majority of the isolates were from the respiratory system (47.7%), followed by wound swab/pus (11.6%/10.5%). Most of the patients with positive *A. baumannii* cultures were from the neonatal unit, pediatric intensive care unit, and surgical intensive care unit (30.2%, 22.1%, and 12.8%, respectively). The results of the antibiotic susceptibility testing revealed a high level of resistance to ampicillin/sulbactam (90.7%), piperacillin (89.5%), ceftazidime

(83.7%), ciprofloxacin (81.4%), meropenem (80.2%), imipenem (77.9%), and cefepime (75.6%). Conversely, the resistance was lowest to colistin (41.9%) and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole (46.5%). Our study highlights a concerning pattern of antibiotic resistance in *A. baumannii* isolates in the classes of antibiotics tested, indicating a high prevalence of multidrug-resistant strains. Appropriate antibiotic administration, rigorous infection control, and antimicrobial stewardship are essential in addressing infections caused by antibiotic-resistant *A. baumannii* in a clinical setting. Additionally, local and national surveillance data must be considered.

7-2404 MP

المحور الطبي

Is health literacy associated with antibiotic use, knowledge, and awareness of antimicrobial resistance among non-medical university students in Tobruk, Libya? A cross-sectional study

Eisa S Omar¹, Hanadi Murajia Abdullah², Hiyam Younes Abdulsiziz², Heba M A Mosa², Rehab Mohammad Abdulghani² & Aeshah Husayn

1. Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Tobruk, Tobruk, Libya.
2. Intern student, Faculty of Medicine, University of Tobruk, Tobruk, Libya.

eisasaleh1987@tu.edu.ly

Abstract

Background: Antibiotic resistance is a global public health concern, especially in developing countries, where antibiotic misuse is widespread. However, studies investigating relevant factors, particularly in youth, are limited. This study examined the levels of health literacy (HL) and their association with antibiotic use, knowledge of antibiotics, and awareness of antibiotic resistance among non-medical Tobruk University students in Tobruk, Libya.

Methodology: A web-based observational cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted using a “Google Form” to obtain responses from non-medical university students during June and July 2023.

Results: Out of 150 participants that filled out the web-based survey, 150 gave their consent for voluntary participation and completed the questionnaire. The mean age of the study participants was 20 years. The proportion of females

(54%) was slightly higher than that of males (45.3%). Half of the respondents (50%) used antibiotics to treat diseases caused by viruses, and another (72.7%) of them said that antibiotics speed up the treatment of colds and coughs. We also found that last year, only (57.3 %) of them used antibiotics without a doctor's prescription.

Conclusion: The current study showed that the students were from different non-medical colleges at the University of Tobruk. Also, it has been observed that gaps in terms of knowledge, attitude, and awareness regarding antibiotic use among students were observed. National Center for Disease Control - Libya should target these gaps, aiming to increase awareness of proper antibiotic use and its association with drug resistance. Enforcing antibiotic regulations at a national level is paramount to targeting over-the-counter sales; hence, reducing self-medication and high rates of consumption.

Keywords: Antibiotics use; antibiotics resistance; knowledge; awareness and Tobruk University.

مقارنة استخلاص الحمض النووي (DNA) الجينومي باستخدام SDS و Triton X-100 في محلول التحلل بطريقة الفينول-كلوروفورم لبكتيريا *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

عبدالسلام سالم ، حواء محمد ، ولاء مادي

قسم علم النبات ، كلية العلوم ، جامعة سبها

abd.saim@sebhou.edu.ly

المُستخلص

استخلاص الحمض النووي (DNA) من مصادره المختلفة هي الخطوة الرئيسية في التطبيقات الجزيئية ويفضل أن يكون DNA المستخلص ذو تركيز ونقاوة عاليين . تهدف هذه الدراسة الى استخلاص DNA الكروموسومي لبكتيريا *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* بطريقة الفينول-كلوروفورم حيث تم استخدام SDS و Triton X-100 كل على حدى بتركيز 10% في محلول التحلل ، وبينت النتائج المتحصل عليها ان DNA المستخلص باستخدام Triton x100 كان اكثر نقاوة من المتحصل عليه باستخدام SDS ، حيث كان معدل النقاوة (A280/260) من البروتينات بمتوسط (1.7) لمركب Triton X-100 ومتوسط (1.0) لمركب SDS ، اما معدل النقاوة (A260/230) من الكربوهيدرات كان متوسط (1.64) لمركب Triton X-100 و متوسط (1.26) لمركب SDS وبينت نتائج التحليل الاحصائي وجود فروق معنوية لمعدلات النقاوة، ولم يكن هنالك فروق معنوية في التركيز المتحصل عليه لكلا المركبين ، تبين هذه الدراسة اهمية استخدام المركبات المختلفة التي تعطي DNA اكثر نقاوة ، وتحتاج المزيد من المعايير والتجارب المتعلقة بتقنية PCR للتعرف على اهمية نقاوة DNA .

7-2419 MP

المحور الطبي

Assessment of anemia and related factors among non-pregnant women

Asmaa Alboeshi¹, Salah Tabbal, Fawzi Ebrahim*

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

fowzi.omer@yahoo.com

Abstract

Background: Anemia is a major cause for maternal mortality and chronic anemia leads to secondary organ damage such as congestive heart failure, Women are more likely to be exposed to anemia than men, which is an epidemic public health problem in Libya. According to the World Bank collection 2019, it is estimated of 29.9 % in non-pregnant women aged 15- 66 years. **Objective:** To determine the prevalence of anemia and related factors among non-pregnant women in Libya. **Method:** This cross-sectional study was randomly selected (134 females) during the period from August to October 2023. Women were given questionnaires regarding their socio-demographic and health characteristics; the data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0 software, Statistical analyses with 95% confidence intervals were considered to be significant if $P < 0.01$. Ethical approval obtained of the Libyan Biotechnology center Committee.

Results: data on one hundred thirty four (69%) non- pregnant female between 15- up to 66 years of age (mean age: 33.82 ± 13.11 years). The study results showed an anemia prevalence of 44.78% (Confidence Interval 43.5 - 46.9%) in the study sample. Similarly, the mean of hematological parameters Hb , Hct, MCV, MCH , MCHC , RDW and Serum ferritin for anemic female participants had significantly level ($p < 0.001$) compared non-anemic female in women according to the world health organization (WHO) defines anemic as hemoglobin concentrations (hemoglobin <12.0 g/dl) the mean Hb values were 10.21 g/dl (95% CI 10.37-11.00g/dl) ($P < 0.0001$). The most prevalent degree was moderate anemia 53.3%, compared to mild and severe anemia were 41.67 % , 5% respectively, we observed a high proportion among women in reproductive age , being's aged 25 - 46 years and heavy menstrual bleeding (HMB) is a factor associated of anemia ($P < 0.001$) .

Conclusion: The most prevalent degree was moderate anemia 53.3%, compared to mild and severe anemia were 41.67 % , 5% respectively, a high prevalence rate of anemia among women in reproductive period , being married 48.3% being overderweights 43.3% or obese 25% , being works 50 % and rural residents 63.3 % . Correspondingly, heavy menstrual bleeding (HMB) highly associated with the development of anemia ($P < 0.001$).

Keywords: Anemia, Anemia severity, world health organization, serum ferritin, reproductive age, heavy menstrual bleeding, related factors.

7-2468 MP

المحور الطبي

Virgin coconut oil carried in solid lipid nanoparticles formula

Abdulfattah I. Abokridiga^{1,*}, Hala I. Alshwaikh¹, Osama Aljewaw¹, Salah Altwanesy, Nagib A. Elmarzugi^{1,2}.

- 1., Libyan Biotechnology Research Center (LARST), Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.
2. Dept. of Industrial Pharmacy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

Abdulfatha@yahoo.co.uk

Abstract

Natural coconut oil is fruit extracted with big potential of nutraceutical and cosmeceutical applications. The Virgin Coconut Oil (VCO) is extracted from fresh coconut through specialized processes without damaging its natural nutrition. VCO has a high content of fatty acids, particularly Lauric acids and has higher phenolic content and antioxidant activity.

After cold press preparation of VCO, centrifugation and chemical method were used for prepare two phase of emulsions and homogenized to prepare nanoemulsion of VCO in solid lipid nanoparticle using ultrasonification equipment to narrow down the size of particle to give Nano size range.

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) are widely used as delivery vehicles for pharmaceutical, cosmeceutical and nutraceuticals. SLNs have a high affinity and bioavailability to skin, which may have potential to ease and fast penetration of nano designed skin formulations.

The average particle size of the nanoemulsion was obtained at fixed period repeatedly were 290nm, which obtained at comparatively low polydisperty about 0.3 pdi, with very well dispersion characteristics. The way of preparation is considered simple and less time consumed. Finally further characterization.

Keywords:coconut oil, solid lipid nanoparticles, cosmeceutical, Nano emulsion.

7-2444 MP

المحور الطبي

COVID-19 Symptoms and Post Complications among Libyans

Mohamed Musbah Aljabri¹, Mofida M. Alfaid², Hafsa A. Alemam¹, Zuhur Lahrsh¹,
Manal Khalifa Hasan², Hajer M Almuaket,¹ Abdounasser Albasher Omar²

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Centre, Tripoli University, Tripoli, Libya.

2. Faculty of Science - Gharyan, University of Gharyan, Libya

mmm_aljabri@hotmail.com

Abstract

The battle against COVID-19 does not always end when recovery is declared. Many individuals confirmed recovered from COVID-19 continue to experience a variety of symptoms. The aim of this study was to shed more light on COVID-19 and post-COVID-19 symptoms in Libya. Two hundred and twenty Libyan individuals (58% female; 42% male), who recovered from COVID-19, were asked to answer a questionnaire that was performed to inquire about the presence of COVID-19 and post-COVID-19 symptoms. Additionally, comorbidities and demographic data were included. The most common comorbidities were hypertension (20%), diabetes (16%), and lung disease (08%). The main COVID-19 symptoms were headache (56%), anosmia and ageusia (52%), Arthralgia (48%), cough (46%) and fever (41%). While the post-COVID-19 symptoms

were fatigue (64%), sleep disorders (52%), insomnia, anxiety, depression (42%), and anosmia and ageusia (32%). Persistent COVID and its related long-term complications may continue to affect patients and their families.

Keywords: COVID-19 symptoms; post-COVID-19; comorbidities.

7-2423 MP

المحور الطبي

Helping Medical Doctors Diagnose Cervical Cancer Using Decision Making based Deep Learning System

Essam Alshareef, Sedigh Abdalla Bashir, Mohamed Burid Milad, Fauzia Ali Abuhtna,

Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli, Libya.

Essam.shref@gmail.com

Abstract

Cervical cancer is a leading cancer in the female population. This disease is considered dangerous as its slow and unpredicted growth. The prevention of such cancer can be mostly achieved by screening its transformation zones. The cervical pre-cancerous zones can be considered as three types: type 1, type 2, and type 3. Screening and analyzing these three stages can be crucial for preventing their transformation into cancer. Hence, it is essentially important to have an automated and intelligent system that can grade the cervical pre-cancerous colposcopy images into one of the three types. This can help in providing the right treatment and prevent cancer transformation. In this paper, we develop a residual learning-based model (ResNet-50) to be trained for classifying the type of a colposcopy cervical image into type 1, type 2, and type 3. Experimentally, the model was fine-tuned and evaluated on a public dataset of colposcopy cervical images and achieved promising results in cervical cancer screening of accuracy of 77% and F1-score of 79%.

Keywords: Cervical cancer, colposcopy, ResNet-50, Residual learning.

7-2448 MP

المحور الطبي

Nutritional status of anemic and non-anemic mothers, and outcomes of neonates born at Zawia Medical Center – Libya

Obaid B. Alwan¹, Zenab Abdulla Mo Elfzzani², Adel Aeyad Mahfoud¹ and Mohamed A. Ebsaim¹

1. Laboratory Department - Faculty of Medical Technology – University of Zawia.

2. Pediatrics Department - Faculty of Medicine - University of Zawia.

o.alwan@zu.edu.ly

Abstract

Background: Anemia is a common medical disorder during pregnancy, especially in third world countries like Libya. Iron deficiency during pregnancy may contribute to health problems and malnutrition during pregnancy.

Objectives: To determine hemoglobin levels in umbilical cord blood and to evaluate the relationship between maternal hemoglobin concentration and perinatal outcomes in Zawia Medical Center

Materials and Methods: This is a cross-sectional study of 81 pregnant women who were admitted to the maternity ward of the Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics/ Zawia Medical Center from 2 July 2022 to 20 September 2022. Blood samples were collected from women in labor in ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) tubes. Immediately, after blood samples were collected, a complete blood count (CBC) test was performed, and in the same context, cord blood samples were examined. Sociodemographic characteristics, perinatal outcomes and nutritional status were obtained by a pre-designed survey and analyzed using SPSS 22.0. Pearson’s correlation and one-way ANOVA were performed to

analyze several variables. Descriptive analysis was used as appropriate. Statistical significance was considered at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: The hemoglobin values of anemic and non-anemic mothers and their neonates were 9.33 ± 1.01 g/dL and 14.44 ± 1.26 g/dL, and 12.12 ± 1.51 g/dL 14.37 ± 2.10 g/dL, respectively. Moderate anemia was the most commonly observed in the study population (24.69%), followed by mild (27.16%) and severe anemia (1.24%). There was a significant correlation between maternal hemoglobin concentration and cord blood hemoglobin concentration (p-value ≤ 0.05). In addition, the study showed that Libyan pregnant mothers concentrate more on consuming traditional local food, some of which are poor in micronutrient contents.

Conclusion: The results of this study showed that the average hemoglobin in newborns was low and there is a direct relationship between maternal and umbilical cord hemoglobin.

Keywords: Pregnancy, Hemoglobin, Anemia, Maternal, Newborns.

7-2471 MP

المحور الطبي

Detection of MUTYH gene mutation of exon 7 in colorectal cancer patients in Misurata

Asma Ali Abudabbous¹

1. Misurata University

Asma.abodabous@gmail.com

Abstract

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the most Dangerous cancers in the world, The early diagnosis of CRC is of essential importance as it is one of the most curable cancers if detected early. So, this study aims to detection of mutations on MUTYH gene in Libyan's families have heredity colorectal cancer. The study included 20 Sample (10 from colorectal cancer patients and 10 from healthy people with CRC family history). the genomic DNA from the samples, the specific region in exon 7 of the target gene (MUTYH) was amplified by PCR using the primers. The PCR products revealed a band of the expected size of the MUTHY gene at 173bp., the mutations were present in 10% (2/20) of all analyzed samples and 60% (12\20) normal and 30% (6/20) exclude, Since there is noise present, hence repetitive sequencing is required. A total of 2 patients had a MUTYH mutations in different positions; of which sample number 8 had a Insertion mutation in c.136 Ins C and sample number 17 had 3 substitution mutation in c.113 A>G , c.142 T>C, c.143 G>A and insertion mutation in two positions c.128 Ins TT and c.165 Ins T. Additional studies will be helpful to identify of new mutations. We believe that an enlargement of the MUTYH mutation spectrum resulting from these types of studies will contribute to early detection and the prevention of secondary cancer development.

7-24119 MP

المحور الطبي

The Effect of Smoking on Platelets Count and Platelets Parameters.

Zaed Mohamed Jaber¹

1. Medical laboratory department, Higher Institute of Sciences and Medical Technology,

Zaidjaberalzaidy@gmail.com

Abstract

Background and objective: Smokers may have increased levels of platelets and platelets agreeability, which may initiate clot formation, or decreased levels which lead to uncontrolled bleeding. This study aimed to investigate, the effect of smoking on platelets counts and platelets parameters include, Mean platelets volume (MPV), Platelets distribution width (PDW), Platelets Large cell ratio (P-LCR), Platelet Crite (PCT).

Material and Methods: Analytical cross-sectional study conducted in the population of Al-khomse- Libya during the period from (Jun to Aug 2022). Ninety-four participants were participated in the study: forty-four smokers and fifty non-smokers, aged between (18-40 years). The smokers consumed at least (5) cigarettes per day for at least one year, and not suffering from any influencing factors.

Results: This study showed that cigarette smoking has no statistically significant effect on platelet count and platelet parameters in smokers compared to non-smokers ($p=0.12$). Moreover, differences in smoking duration including (1–5, 5–10 and over 10years) and also the difference in the amount

of cigars smoked per day had no statistical effect on platelet count and platelet parameters in the smoker population, and the p-values were 0.10 and 0.25, respectively.

Conclusion: The study concluded that the platelet counts, and platelet parameters had no statistical significant difference between smokers and non-smokers as well as between different smoking periods and different smoking amounts.

Keywords: Platelets, smokers.

7-2408 MP

المحور الطبي

Antibacterial Activity of *Silybum marianum L.*, Against Methicillin Resistance *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Ali A. Abeed¹, Dua Ali Abu-Qsea¹, Hadeel Essa Salem¹,
Marwah Mohamed Barashin¹

1. Department of Medical Laboratory, Yefren Collage of Medical Technology,
Yefren, Libya

ali66abeid66@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: This research discusses the screening of phytochemical constituents and antibacterial activity of *Silybum marianum* (milk thistle) leaves against methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). Aim: The aim of this research was to screen some phytochemical constituents of the *Silybum marianum* leaves, in addition to study their antibacterial activity against MRSA. Methods: The study involved collecting and preparing the leaves of the plant, calculating the productive yield of the extract, conducting qualitative phytochemical tests, and determining the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bacterial concentration (MBC) of the extract against MRSA.

Results: The results showed that the extract contained saponins, flavonoids, and alkaloids, and exhibited antibacterial activity against MRSA with an MIC and MBC of 25mg/ml and 50mg/ml, respectively.

Conclusion: The study highlights the potential of natural herbal drugs as an alternative to synthetic medicaments for treating bacterial infections, especially those caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria.

Keywords: Silybium marinum, Phytochemicals, Flavonoids, MRSA, iMLSB, Libya.

7-2483 MP

المحور الطبي

Enhancing Precision Drug Therapy and build pharmacokinetic model in Pregnant Women: PBPK Modeling of Antiviral drugs

Ashraf.A. Naass¹, Mohamed Abdulsamed¹, Mohamed.S.AEswani¹. Sedigh Bashir¹

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli, Libya.

ashraf.naas@btc.org.ly

Abstract

PBPK/PD modeling is essential in modern drug development. Traditional drug development methods frequently rely on trial and error, which can be time-consuming, costly, and could be risky. Predicting pharmacokinetics (PK) of drugs in pregnant women, encompassing the intricate aspect of placental drug transfer, remains a complex task. This study was to compare of simulated or predicted and observed (previously published approaches) pharmacokinetic parameters among the four antiviral drugs in pregnant and non-pregnant women. In addition, this investigation endeavors to construct and assess physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models specific to maternal-fetal interactions for four antiviral drugs, Acyclovir, Emtricitabine, Dolutegravir (DTG) and Raltegravir (RAL). PBPK models were built with the Open Systems Pharmacology software suite (PK-Sim/MoBi). Different approaches to inform placental drug transfer were applied and compared. Model performance was evaluated using in vivo all 4 a forementioned antiviral maternal plasma concentrations during the 2nd and 3rd trimesters and umbilical vein concentrations at delivery. All clinical in vivo data were obtained from the

International Maternal paediatric and Adolescent AIDS Clinical Trials (IMPAACT) Network P1026s study. The PBPK models successfully predicted plasma concentration-time profiles of four antiviral drugs in the 2nd and 3rd trimesters and most predicted PK parameters fell within a 1.33-fold error range. Predicted umbilical vein concentrations of DTG among others were in reasonable agreement with in vivo data but were sensitive to changes in the placental partition coefficient and transplacental clearance. Maternal-fetal PBPK modeling reliably predicted maternal PK of previously mentioned antiviral during pregnancy. For the fetal PK, data on the unbound fraction of highly protein-bound DTG has proven to be important to adequately capture changes in total clearance in silico. More research efforts, along with clinical data, are needed to verify the predictions of fetal PK of antiviral. In conclusion, the findings suggest the feasibility of employing physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models to assess the disposition of antiviral drugs in pregnant women and their fetuses.

Keywords: Pharmacokinetic, Modeling, Pregnancy, Antiviral drugs, PBPK. Maternal-fetal.

7-24110 MP

المحور الطبي

Molecular Characterization of Gram- Negative Bacteria Producing Metallo-Beta-Lactamase from Teaching Hospitals in Benghazi, Libya

Asma Elramli^{1*2}, Ameni Arfaoui³, Siham Agouri⁴, Meha Fathi ³Marwa .M.Attayeb⁵,
Nouel klibi³ and Hadda-Imene Ouzari

1. Department of Medical Technology, College of Science and Technology-Qaminis, Libya
2. Alakeed Laboratory, Benghazi, Libya.
- 3.Laboratory of Microorganisms and Active Biomolecules, MBA-LR03ES03, Faculty of Sciences of Tunis, University of Tunis El Manar, Tunis, Tunis
- 4.Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, University of Benghazi, Libya.
5. Libyan Biotechnology Research Centre, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

asmaelrammly@yahoo.com

Abstract

Introduction: In Libya, MDR bacterial prevalence and their rates have increased especially among Gram-negative bacteria has been increasing in recent years. Probably due to abuse of antimicrobials including carbapenems and extended spectrum beta lactamase (ESBL) in Libyan hospitals and poor applied the infection control practices, mortality and morbidity caused by multidrug resistant (MDR) Gram-negative bacteria , especially *A.baumannii* , *K.pneumoniae*. limitations to effective antimicrobial agent's administration, is still challenging and lead to significant infection control problems

Aim : To evaluate the prevalence of multi-drug resistant *A.bumannii*. and other pathogens, and study molecular characteristics of resistance to beta lactams antimicrobials.

Materials and Methods: This study has been implemented at teaching hospitals in Benghazi city. 500 samples were collected from clinical and environmental samples , The procedure for processing of samples, identification, susceptibility to common used antimicrobials and evidence of MBL strains were carried out according to the recommended standards. PCR was used to detect carbapenemase resistance genes and sent to sequencing.

Results: *k.pneumoniae* and *Abumannii* were the most prevalent bacteria and cause mortality in ICU (42.5% , 41%). These isolates exhibited high resistance to all used antibiotics except colistin (100%) . ninety- two(92%) of the isolates were MBL producers. were identified by *bla_{NDM}*, *bla_{VIM}* *bla_{IMP}* ,.in Our study shows the high rate of MDR and XDR in clinical *and environmental* isolates in hospitals.

Keywords: Acinetobacter Bumannii, K. pneumoniae, β -lactamase, MDR/XDR, PCR Analysis, Resistance gens.

7-24136 MP

المحور الطبي

Prevalence of Cardiovascular Disease and its Complications in Young Women in Libya: A Cross-Sectional survey

Sarah Abdulrazik¹, Eiman Elhouderi², Ghufran Alshakshouki¹, Naqa Bilwas¹,
Elham Omran Elgdhafi³, Inas Alhudiri^{1*}

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli, Libya

2. Harvard Medical School, Boston, USA

3. Cardiology Department, Faculty of Medicine, University of Tripoli

einasse@gmail.com

Abstract

Introduction

Cardiovascular disease is the major cause of death in Libya. A study showed that the incidence of ischemic heart disease is about 43% in 2019 among Libyan women. There are limited studies regarding the current status of cardiovascular diseases in young women and cardiovascular disease risk factors.

Aim

We aim to assess the prevalence of cardiovascular diseases in young Libyan women and associated risk factors.

Methods

An online survey was conducted during March 2023. The survey targeted women participants aged 18-55 years from northern, southern, and mid regions of Libya.

Results

The mean age of the study population was 29.54 ± 9.3 years. Over half of the women (53.2%) were either overweight or obese. Additionally, 52.8% had a family history of diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, or obesity. The most commonly used oil was corn oil (67%), followed by olive oil (11%). A majority of participants (84%) reported eating white bread daily, and 64.7% consumed full-fat milk daily. Physical activity levels were low, with 82% of participants reporting a sedentary lifestyle. Sleep duration was typically between 5-8 hours, with 70% of participants falling within this range.

Conclusion

This study found a high prevalence of cardiovascular disease risk factors among young Libyan women. These findings are concerning as they suggest that young Libyan women are at increased risk of developing cardiovascular disease later in life. Interventions are needed to address these risk factors and improve the cardiovascular health of young Libyan women.

7-24138 MP

المحور الطبي

Prevalence of smell and taste disturbance after COVID-19 infection and its impact on lifestyle among university students in Libya.

Retaj Kasm Agha¹, Mohamed Said¹, Mohamed Elghazal¹, Yara Talal Mohammed¹, Anas Mohammed Aboutartour¹, Mosab Emhemmed Matous¹, Mohammed Hejaaji³, Feras Mohamed Shneib¹, Inas Alhudiri^{3*}

1. Faculty of Medicine, University of Tripoli, Tripoli, Libya

2. University of Warwick, Warwick, UK

3. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli, Libya

inas.alhudiri@btc.org.ly

Abstract

Background COVID-19 can cause a range of symptoms, including loss of smell and taste. These sensory disturbances can significantly impact daily life, affecting both personal and social interactions. This study aimed to examine the prevalence of smell and taste disturbances among COVID-19-infected individuals.

Methods This cross-sectional study examined the prevalence of smell and taste disturbances among 600 COVID19-infected individuals from universities in Tripoli, Libya. Data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire between July 2021 and January 2023.

Results Among the 600 participants, 501 reported smell disturbances, and 449 reported taste disturbances.

Sixteen individuals had not regained their sense of smell, and ten had not regained their sense of taste. 5.4% reported having an accident due to either smell and 11.8 due to taste disturbance. 15% felt very handicapped and 21% felt slightly handicapped because of their smell/taste disturbance. 17.6% reported that it very much affected their lifestyle and eating habits, 34.5% slightly affected their lifestyle and eating habits. 9% consulted a psychiatrist. 45.3%. Approximately 23% of participants sought medical advice for their sensory disturbances. Sex and smoking status were not found to be associated with the loss of smell or taste.

Conclusions Smell and taste disturbances are common among COVID-19-infected individuals and can persist for an extended period. Further research is needed to identify risk factors for these sensory disturbances and develop effective treatment approaches.

7-24139 MP

المحور الطبي

Estimation of Prediabetes and its Risk factors in Libyan population: a cross-sectional survey

Wafeya S. Atwear¹, Fouzia Abd. Aldaba¹, Ahmed Elkikkli¹, Khaled Abdelsalam², Abdulmunam A. Fellah¹, Zakarya Abusrewil³, Inas M Alhudiri^{1*}

1.Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

2. migration health division, International organization for migration, Tripoli, Libya.

3. Medical ward, Tripoli University Hospital, Tripoli, Libya

inas.alhudiri@btc.org.ly

Abstract

Background It is estimated that the frequency of prediabetes is increasing worldwide. Individuals with prediabetes are at high risk for developing type 2 diabetes. This study aims to assess the frequency of prediabetes and diabetes and their associated risk factors among adults in Libya.

Methods

A cross-sectional survey was conducted for patients attending a family health clinic in Tripoli for regular check-up. Prediabetes was defined as having FBS 100 to 125 and HbA1C 5.7% to 6.4% according to ADA. Participants completed a medical history and lifestyle questionnaire and had their blood pressure, waist circumference, height and weight measured and blood samples taken. Hemodynamic parameters were measured using photoplethysmography and pulse pressure wave analysis.

Blood sugar and HbA1C were tested to assess glycemic state.

Results

39.3% of whom were men and 60.7% of whom were women. Mean fasting blood sugar and HbA1c were 91.1 mg/dl and 5.9% respectively. The prevalence of prediabetes according to impaired fasting glucose was 11.2% and the prevalence of prediabetes according to HbA1c was 8.4% (5.7%-6.4%). About 36.4% were overweight and 41.1 % were obese. Average systemic vascular resistance (SVR) was 1376.4 ± 236.86 dynes· sec/cm⁵. Diabetic patients in this study population were 5.6%.

Conclusion

The prevalence of obesity and overweight is high in this study exceeding 60% in total. SVR results indicate higher risk for atherosclerosis and hypertension. These findings suggest that there is a need for increased screening and early detection of prediabetes and diabetes. There is also a need for interventions to prevent the development of prediabetes and diabetes, such as lifestyle modifications and weight loss programs.

Keywords: Prediabetes, risk factor, Diabetes Mellitus, metabolic syndrome, Libyan population.

7-2459 MP

المحور الطبي

Isolation and Characterization of Beta-Sitosterol of *Arum cyrenaicum* corms

Laila Ben Ramadan¹, Mohamed Alshintari¹, Abdurzag Zwawi² and Abdurzag Auzi³

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli, Libya.

2. Faculty of Medicine, Tripoli University-Tripoli, Libya.

3. Faculty of Pharmacy, Tripoli University-Tripoli, Libya.

lailabenramadan18@gmail.com

Abstract

The aim of this study is to identify and characterized the bioactive compounds from the corms of the plant. Preliminary phytochemical screening of the extract of *Arum cyrenaicum* corms revealed the presence of steroids, terpenoids, saponins, flavonoids and carbohydrate. The plant belongs to Araceae family, has wide folk medicinal use in traditional medicine. The air dried corms were pulverized to powder, subjected to hot extraction (soxhlet) with chloroform, methanol, and water. Methanolic extract as bioactive fraction based on sensitivity test was subjected to TLC and column chromatography. The isolated compound was white crystalline substance, which was further subjected to physical properties and ¹HNMR for proper characterization and elucidation of the structure. The compound was concluded as β -Sitosterol, this phytosterol is reduce serum LDL cholesterol concentration and anticancer especially breast and prostate cancer.

Keywords: *Arum cyrenaicum* , phytosterol, β -Sitosterol.

7-24137 MP

المحور الطبي

Frequency Distribution of Familial Mediterranean fever (MEFV) gene polymorphisms among Libyan population

Abdussamee A Frefer¹, Inas Alhudiri¹, Mwada Jallul¹, Adam Elzagheid¹, Nabil S. Enattah^{1*}

1. Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli-Libya.

nabil.enattah@yahoo.com

Abstract

Background:

Familial Mediterranean fever is an autosomal recessive disorder. It affects primarily people of Mediterranean origin. No carrier estimates are available for the Libyan population.

Aim:

This study aims to investigate genetic variants in Exons 5 and 10 of MEFV gene in healthy Libyan population.

Methods:

Genomic DNA was extracted from 159 buccal samples. The primers flanking the variants detected within MEFV gene were used for PCR, followed by Sanger sequencing and variant analysis.

Results:

Six coding sequence variants were identified in this study (L710P, K618R, N610D, M694V, P706= and D510=). The carrier rate of pathogenic mutations among random samples of Libyan individuals in this study was 0.6% (M694V).

Conclusions:

MEFV genetic variants are frequent in healthy Libyan individuals across different ethnic groups. The carrier rate of pathogenic mutations in Libyan individuals in this study was much lower than expected and larger sample size should be studied with sequencing for exon 2.

7-2450 MP

المحور الطبي

A study on patients' selection for *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* mutations testing by different models in Libyan women with breast cancer

Eanas Elmaihub^{1*}, Inas Alhudiri², Adam Elzagheid², Fakria Elfagi³ and Elham Hassen^{1,4}

1. Department of Molecular biology, Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Monastir, Monastir University, Monastir, Tunisia.
2. Libyan Biotechnology Research Centre, Tripoli University, Tripoli, Libya.
3. Department of Oncology, National Cancer Institute, Sabratha, Libya.
4. laboratory of Molecular Immuno-Oncology, Faculty of Medicine, Monastir University, Monastir, Tunisia.

eanasaltiari@gmail.com

Abstract

Introduction: The *BRCA* mutation spectrum of familial breast cancer in Libya remains unknown. Several genetic models developed to predict the probability of *BRCA1/2* mutations have not been applied in Libya, where the NCCN criteria are used for highly penetrating breast cancer susceptibility genes. We aimed to predict *BRCA1/2* mutation probability in familial breast cancer and genetic testing eligibility using BOADICEA and BRCAPRO models and NCCN criteria.

Methods: *BRCA1/2* mutations were retrospectively predicted in 62 women with familial breast cancer between 2018 and 2021. Logistic regression, ROC analysis, and area under curve were used to compare NCCN referral criteria

with the BRCAPRO and BOADICEA scores.

Results: Thirty-two out of 62 breast cancer patients (51.6%), with a mean age of 43.5 ± 8 years, were predicted as *BRCA* mutation carriers by both models. BRCAPRO predicted *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* mutations in 27.4% and 41.9% of the women, respectively. BOADICEA predicted 8% for *BRCA1* and 29% for *BRCA2*. At least one NCCN criterion was met by 50/62 women (80.6%). Three criteria were statistically significant predictors in BRCAPRO and BOADICEA: breast cancer at ≤ 50 years with one or more close blood relatives with breast cancer, breast cancer patient with a close relative of male breast cancer, and triple-negative breast cancer. For the three respective criteria, sensitivity was 0.78, 0.89 and 0.75, specificity was 0.33, 0.39 and 0.22, area under curve was 0.72, 0.75 and 0.76, positive predictive value was 55%, 61% and 51%, and negative predictive value was 58.5%, 77% and 45%. **Conclusions:** Our study highlights that certain aspects of the NCCN criteria demonstrate variations in significance when compared to the BRCAPRO and BOADICEA models. For the first time, these models were used to predict *BRCA* mutations in Libyan women, and our finding indicates that these models are promising for improving genetic testing decision-making.

Keywords: *Breast cancer, NCCN criteria, BRCAPRO, BOADICEA, BRCA1, BRCA2.*

7-24333MP

المحور الطبي

Application of forensic RNA analysis as a method for body fluid stain age prediction

Dr Fisal Asaghiar

Ministry of Interior ,Criminal Investigation Department (CID) ,Tripoli-Libya.

Abstract

The basic questions that must be answered during the crime investigation is who left the biological evidence and when. DNA profiling can, in most cases, successfully identify the person who deposited the sample, leaving, therefore, as the main concern question about the length of time between deposition of the stain and its subsequent recovery. It is widely accepted that the level of RNA in the sample decreases over time. Therefore, reverse transcription quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) method was performed to quantify the selected markers and investigate how they degrade as a function of time. *Hypoxia inducible factor 1A* (HIF1A) were therefore investigated using TaqMan and SYBR Green chemistries. Single and multiple regression analysis were employed in data analysis, which suggested that some of tested markers could be used to predict the stain age.

7-2426 MP

المحور الطبي

Clinical outcome and CD20 expression alteration in Libyan B-cell lymphoma patients treated with Rituximab

EShawesh EI, Abulayha AM, Tabal SA, Elbasir MA, Elbanani AS

Libyan Biotechnology Research Center, Tripoli University, Tripoli, Libya.

ee-manib@yahoo.com

Abstract

Rituximab is a chimeric IgG1 monoclonal antibody raised against the B-cell CD20 surface molecule. CD20 is expressed on normal B cells as well as on more than 90% of non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (NHL). The killing mechanisms of rituximab involve complement-dependent and antibody-dependent cellular cytotoxicity and induction of apoptosis. The aim of this study was to use flow cytometry technology to monitor the depletion of CD20-positive B cells in Libyan lymphoma patients treated with Rituximab. Peripheral blood samples were collected from twenty five Libyan lymphoma patients undergoing Rituximab treatment in the oncology department of Tripoli Medical Center and the National Cancer Institute Sabratha. The results showed that twenty four patients had a complete depletion of B cells following the third cycle of Rituximab treatment. However, one patient was resistant to the effect of Rituximab, and B cells stayed resistant until the seventh cycle when the patient was pull out of Rituximab treatment. Overall, the results of this study presents flow cytometry data describing the efficacy of Rituximab in Libyan B cell lymphoma.

Keywords: Rituximab, CD20, B-cell Lymphoma, flow cytometry.